

A Study on the Attitude of Secondary School Teachers towards Flipped Learning and Flipped Learning Material

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“I never teach my pupils, I only attempt to provide the conditions in which they can learn.”

Albert Einstein

Abstract

Worldwide, institutions and universities are increasingly debating the integration of digital technologies in educational settings. A flipped learning method has been perceived as a way to respond to the questions of teachers and meet the needs of students. Flipping learning has thus become a trend among teachers in order to keep up with 21st century issues and improve student learning outcomes. The integration of these technologies appears to be met with cynicism and reluctance by teachers. A change in attitudes among teachers towards new technologies is therefore urgently needed. This research study is conducted through the use of a questionnaire on teachers of private as well as government secondary schools to inquire upon their attitudes towards flipped learning and flipped learning material. The results of the investigation depict that approx 55% teachers thought that flipped learning is a better teaching learning approach than conventional. 72% teachers showed their zeal and enthusiasm towards flipped learning and make use of it in their classes.

Keywords:- Flipped Learning, Flipped Learning Material, Attitude, and Secondary School Teachers.

Conceptual Background of the Study:-

In flipped learning, instructional content is delivered outside of the classroom, often online, and activities, like homework, are moved into the classroom, often via webcasting. Flipped learning involves watching lectures online, participating in online discussions, or carrying out research at home before integrating concepts from a lecture into a classroom lesson.

In flipped learning, lectures and homework are reversed and part of the course is flipped. Before the class session, students watch short video lectures, and in-class time is dedicated to exercises, projects, or discussions. Flipped learning typically involves video lectures, which are either created by the instructor and posted online or selected from a repository. It is certainly possible to use an audio podcast to record and listen to a prerecorded lecture, but video today is so accessible that the flipped model is so closely associated with it.

The attitude has been central to the explanation of social behavior throughout the history of social psychology. In general, the term refers to a positive or negative reaction towards an object, person, or event. Different degrees of favorability can be held by individuals toward themselves and their surroundings. Because attitudes are hypothetical constructs, they are inferred from measurable responses reflecting positive or negative evaluations of the attitudes they describe. It is possible to infer attitudes from cognitive responses or beliefs (reflecting a person's perception, and information, of, the attitude object). Three categories of responses are distinguished, following a classification dating back to Plato:

attitudes can be determined by cognitive responses or beliefs; affective reactions (evaluating the object and feeling about it); and conative responses.

Significance of the Study:-

In 21st century it is the need for schools to change their approach towards teaching and learning process. Now technology has become an essential part of education and it is the responsibility of schools to develop thinking skills, ICT skills, heuristic and creative attitude of learners which is the demand of 21st century. Flipped learning is also an approach which helps the students to empower them with choices. To make students' learning permanent it is necessary to make their learning active. Flipped learning promotes new pattern of thinking among students. They experience their own learning and directly explore their own knowledge. This learning approach makes the learners responsible towards their studies and the teachers can guide them for higher order thinking and higher levels of applications. This study aimed at investigating the attitude of secondary school teachers towards Flipped Learning and Flipped Learning Material.

Statement of Problem:- “A Study on the Attitude of Secondary School Teachers towards Flipped Learning and Flipped Learning Material”

Operational Definition of Key Words:-

Flipped Learning: Flipped learning is a method in which the traditional idea of classroom-based learning is turned upside down. Students are given the learning material ahead of time, and during class, they discuss it with their peers and engage in problem-solving activities with the help of the teacher.

Flipped Learning Material: FLM is prepared by teachers and introduced to the students outside the class. Mostly it is provided online and it consists with videos, audios, presentations, text material etc. So, FLM helps students to enter in the class with a conceptual knowledge he/she attains before the class.

Attitude: Attitude refers to a person's mental outlook, perspective, or disposition towards something or someone. It is a state of mind that influences how individuals think, feel, and behave in various situations. Attitude can be positive, negative, or neutral, and it can be shaped by personal beliefs, experiences, values, and social influences.

Secondary School Teachers: Secondary school teachers provide education to students ranging from 6th to 12th grade.

Objectives:-

1. To study the attitude of secondary school teachers towards Flipped Learning and Flipped Learning Material.
2. To study the awareness secondary school teachers towards Flipped Learning and Flipped Learning Material.

Delimitations:-

1. This study is delimited to the city 'Rohtak' only.
2. This study is delimited to Flipped Learning, Flipped Learning Material and attitude of teacher secondary school teachers only.
3. This study is delimited to sample size of 110 teachers only.

Research Type:-

This study used descriptive research approach.

Research Methodology:-

This study is based on a quantitative analysis of a closed questionnaire addressing secondary school teachers' attitude towards flipped learning and flipped learning material.

Variables of the Study:-

In the present study three variables have been studied.

1. Flipped Learning
2. Flipped Learning Material
3. Attitude

Sample Size:-

Sample size refers to the number of observations or individuals included in a study or experiment. It is an important consideration in research because the size of the sample can influence the reliability and validity of the results. The size of sample is of 110 Teachers (51 Male, 59 Female) for this study.

Tools:-

A closed questionnaire (Google Form) consists with 15 questions to measure the attitude of secondary school teachers towards flipped learning and flipped learning material.

Statistical Technique:-

The data are analyzed based on these sections. A closed questionnaire consists with 15 questions was prepared where nine items were designed to express the level of agreement and disagreements with specific items on a five-point Likert scale (i.e., strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree) and six items were designed to express the thinking of secondary school teachers about flipped learning and flipped learning material with specific items on a three-point scale (i.e., Yes, No, Maybe). The data were statistically analyzed from the submitted responses. Independent-samples t-test was used to test a comparison of mean between males' and females' secondary school to analyze teachers' attitudes towards flipped learning and flipped learning material.

Results and Interpretation:-
Teacher's Profile:-

Table 1.1: Results of the Attitude Questionnaire

Sr. No.	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Flipped learning is a better teaching learning approach than conventional teaching learning approach.	7.3%	10.9%	16.4%	54.5%	10.9%
2	Flipped learning makes the classroom more interactive.	9.1%	8.2%	12.7%	49.1%	20.9%
3	Flipped learning motivated the learners more.	7.3%	6.4%	11.8%	54.5%	20%
4	Flipped learning makes the learners more active.	5.5%	6.3%	18.2%	53.6%	16.4%
5	Learners learn more and better with flipped learning approach.	5.5%	9.1%	15.4%	53.6%	16.4%
6	Flipped learning material makes learners more responsible and sincere towards their studies.	9.1%	9.1%	22.7%	48.2%	10.9%
7	Flipped leaning material boosts the grade of learners.	11.8%	8.2%	10.9%	54.5%	14.6%
8	Flipped learning material makes learning easy, enjoyable and stress-free.	8.2%	2.7%	20%	45.5%	23.6%
9	Flipped learning approach establishes better teacher learner rapport.	10%	8.1%	17.3%	49.1%	15.5%

Sr. No.	Statement	Yes	No	Maybe
10	Do you think flipped learning materials are effective learning resources?	68.2%	12.7%	19.1%
11	Do you think learners could focus more on their study through flipped learning material?	67.3%	16.4%	16.3%
12	Do you think learners are confident to do the problems before coming to class after watching the material?	70.9%	13.6%	15.5%
13	Do you think flipped learning material helps learners to clear their concepts and deepen their knowledge?	70.9%	13.6%	15.5%
14	Do you think flipped learning approach is more engaging and participating teaching approach?	68.2%	16.4%	15.4%
15	Would you like to prefer the flipped learning approach in your classroom?	71.8%	14.6%	13.6%

Findings of the Study:-

The above table mentions the responses of secondary school teachers towards flipped learning and flipped learning material. By analyzing the responses the following findings were emerged.

1. 55% of the teachers opinioned that flipped learning is a better teaching learning approach than conventional teaching learning approach.

2. 49% of the teachers opinioned that flipped learning make the classroom more interactive.
3. 55% of the teachers said that flipped learning motivated the learners more.
4. 54% of the teachers said that flipped learning makes the learners more active.
5. 54% of teachers opinioned that learners learn more and better with flipped learning approach.

6. 48% of the secondary school teachers said that flipped learning material makes learners more responsible and sincere towards their studies.
7. 55% of teachers believed that flipped learning material boosts the grade of learners.
8. 46% of the teachers believed that flipped learning material makes learning easy, enjoyable and stress-free.
9. 49% of the teachers thought that flipped learning approach establish better teacher learner rapport.
10. 68% of teachers thought that flipped learning materials are effective learning resources.
11. 67% of teachers thought that learners could focus more on their study through flipped learning material.
12. 71% of teachers thought that learners are confident to do the problems before coming to class after watching the material.
13. 71% of teachers thought that flipped learning material helps learners to clear their concepts and deepen their knowledge.
14. 68% of secondary teachers thought that flipped learning approach is more engaging and participating teaching approach.
15. 72% of teachers preferred the flipped learning approach in your classroom.

Suggestions for further Study:-

Research in any branch of human knowledge is never a closed book; there is always a persistent need of finding solution to new problem and testing the veracity of solution of older problems, some of the suggestions for the further researchers in the area are given below:

1. The study can be conducted to other district of Haryana.
2. The study can be conducted to a large sample than selected for the present study which can make the result more reliable.
3. The study can be conducted on students other than school teachers.
4. Similar study can be analyzed by different statistical techniques for verifying the results.
5. The presented study may be extended to rural & urban areas separately.

Conclusion:-

This study aimed at examining secondary school teachers' attitudes toward flipped learning and flipped learning material. The study results revealed that (1) teachers expressed positive attitudes overall toward flipped learning and flipped learning material, (2) teachers agreed on the benefits of flipped learning and flipped learning material regarding teacher–student interaction; (3) teachers expressed skepticism regarding the effects of this teaching approach on parent–student communication.

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